

Kinetics of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Malonic Acid by Acid Bromate[#]

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Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of malonic acid has been studied by a number of workers using various oxidants¹. The mechanistic pathways described are not equivocal as there is no clear evidence presented for the nature of bond fission, whether it is C-C or C-H. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to study the Ru^{III}-catalysed oxidation of malonic acid by acid bromate to throw light on the nature of oxidation, vis-a-vis oxidation of oxalic acid where it is obviously a reaction involving C-C cleavage.

Results and Discussion

Malonic acid is not oxidised in the absence of Ru^{III}. Hence, Ru^{III} has been used as a catalyst to effect the oxidation by acid bromate in aqueous and aqueous acetic acid mixtures in presence of perchloric acid.

The order with respect to bromate has been found to be one. This is different from the reported order in bromate in presence of Mn^{II} indicating that the reaction sequences are different in two reactions². Plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs t are quite linear and the k_1 values obtained are reasonably constant as seen in the effect of change in the concentration of bromate on reaction kinetics. Thus the order with respect to bromate is found to be one. The order with respect to malonic acid is unity as seen from the perfect $\log(b-x)$ vs time plots from each individual run. The decrease in rate constant with increase in concentration of malonic acid has to be explained. It is postulated that it may be due to some inert complexes that are formed between malonic acid

and bromate. Similar decrease in rate has been reported in reactions of ethyl alcohol and Ce^{IV} and also with benzaldehyde and Ce^{IV} where the 1:2 complex is reported to be inert which is the causative factor for the decrease in rate with increase in concentration. The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs [substrate] yields a slope which gives the ratio of the inactive and active forms of the complex. This value is fairly high indicating the formation of inactive complex which is the reason for observed decrease in rate with increasing [substrate].

The order with respect to Ru^{III} is two, much against the general nature of Ru^{III} in many reactions where the first order dependence on Ru^{III} has been postulated. Increase in the [acid] shows that the reaction is insensitive in the range studied. The increase in the percentage of CH₃COOH results in the increase in rate in the range studied (10-50%). But the rates in aqueous medium and aqueous acetic acid medium show that there is a decrease in rate. The reaction rate increases with increase in acetic acid and the obvious reason is that the reaction is favoured in a mixture of low dielectric constant in aqueous acetic acid mixtures. This may not be the case when one deals with pure aqueous system. Factors like internal dielectric constant, cohesive of the solvent and solute-solvent interaction may be playing part. The details are included in Table 1.

The rates have been measured at different temperatures (60, 70 and 80°) and the activation parameters, viz. activation energy, heat of activation and entropy of activation are respectively 21.676 kcal mol⁻¹, 21.014 kcal mol⁻¹ and -15.6 e.s.u. Based

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The order with respect to acid bromate in the oxidation of oxalic acid is one as seen from the linearity of $\log(a-x)$ vs time plots. A perusal of Table 1 indicates the constancy of k_1 with increasing concentration of the oxidant confirming the first order nature with respect to oxidant. The order with respect to oxalic acid is one (Table 1); the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log S$ is unity. The increase in concentration of acid increases the rate till $0.275 M H^+$ and above $0.275 M H^+$ independence to H^+ has been observed. The plot of $\log k$ vs $\log H^+$ is unity indicating the participation of a proton in lower ranges and at higher acidities there is independence of H^+ , unlike in the catalysed oxidation of malonic acid where independence to acidity has been observed throughout the range studied. The increase in percentage of acetic acid increases the rate and this is due to the reaction being favoured in a medium of low dielectric constant. The details are given in Table 1.

The reaction was studied at different temperatures and Arrhenius parameters, viz. activation energy, heat of activation and entropy of activation respectively are $24.024 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $23.402 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and -3.25 e.s.u.

The reaction on the basis of the above facts is routed as follows :

The stoichiometry has been found to be 3 : 1 (oxalic acid : bromate).

In summary, the oxidation of oxalic acid takes place even in the absence of Ru^{III} whereas malonic acid is not oxidised in the absence of Ru^{III} in spite of the fact that it has a reactive methylene group. Ru^{III} does not catalyse the oxidation of oxalic acid whereas oxidation of malonic acid occurs smoothly. Two different mechanisms, one involving C-C fission in the case of oxalic acid and the other involving C-H fission in the case of malonic acid are postulated.

Experimental

Malonic acid, oxalic acid and all other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade. The reaction was followed by estimating the bromate iodometrically. $RuCl_3$ solution was standardised by the reported method⁴. The stoichiometry was found to be 3 : 2 (malonic acid : bromate), the product being formaldehyde (keeping $[\text{malonic acid}] < [\text{BrO}_3^-]$ and estimating the unreacted bromate).

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